

Todo List Application Using Spring Boot

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Abstract:- A list of things that need to be done, often arranged in priority order, is called a to-do list. It is one of the most straightforward approaches to task management and offers a straightforward yet stylish way to organise the things one has to complete.

Keywords:- *Todo list application; Spring Boot; User interface maven provided design; Front-end development; API integration; Real-time; Cross-browser compatibility; Mobile-friendly design; Scalability; Security.*

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ *A To Do list is what?*

The explanation is straightforward. They are usually arranged according to priority. With the advancement of technology, we are now able to construct to-do lists using a variety of tools, including Microsoft To-Do and Google To-Do lists, word documents, email lists, to-do list applications, and excel spreadsheets.

By giving the items on your list a priority order, you can easily determine which ones require your urgent attention and which ones you can put off until later.

One of the most crucial justifications for using a to-do list is that it will keep you organised. Your chores appear more doable when you list them all. It is easier to keep focused when you have a clear list of the things you need to complete and those you have already done.

You can cross items off your list as you finish them. If you're constantly hurrying from one task to the next, you won't feel like you're making progress or doing anything. A sense of accomplishment encourages and drives you to keep going forward.

But having a to-do list has other advantages as well.

➤ *More examples follow: increases memory:*

A to-do list serves as an outside reminder. Only a limited amount of information may be stored at once. You'll be able to remember everything, rather than just a few of the things you need to do, if you keep a to-do list. Additionally, the information will be reinforced by your to-do list, decreasing the likelihood that you'll forget.

Increased Productivity: The list helps to arrange the tasks such that the most important ones are at the top and least important ones are at the bottom.

Helps motivate: Long-term goals can be broken down into smaller, achievable short-term goals. Checking off each one from the list will boost your confidence.

Putting pen to paper and taking the time to create a written list of tasks seems like such a simple solution. A good and convenient plan help in making the day more efficient and better than the day without the planning. By not wasting time trying to identify the next or even more important.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social media and other readily available internet distractions make it difficult for us to maintain our attention on our duties and hinder our ability to do our work effectively.

Additionally, bouncing between things frequently may give us the impression that we are being productive when we are not. Instead of concentrating on crossing off tiny items from our to-do list only for show, it is more vital for us to prioritise chores and work on those that are most significant.

This software aims to increase our awareness of how we spend our time performing certain jobs and the effectiveness of that time. Setting limits on social media can assist to cut down on distractions and keep track of the time we spend working on to-do items. We are able to better manage our daily routines when we have a better understanding of the estimated time we will need to spend on our duties, coupled with the validated time spent on the items for reference or personal/team reviews.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

The current todo list web application is built using traditional web development technologies, such as HTML, CSS, and Java. The website is a collection of web pages that are served by a server to the client's browser upon request. The web pages are static and do not update dynamically based on user input.

The application has a basic user interface that is not very engaging or user-friendly. The website's design is static and does not change based on user input. Users must navigate through different pages to view the various packages and services offered by the website.

Overall, the current todo list application is outdated and does not meet the requirements of modern users. A more modern and dynamic website built using maven can provide

users with a more engaging and userfriendly interface, improve performance, and increase customer satisfaction.

IV. TECHNOLOGY AND TOOLS REQUIRED

➤ JAVA

Java is among one of the best languages which currently can be used for developing web applications backend architecture .It is one of the most widely used language in the web industry .The backend language to be used must only be java as only java has support of spring framework for web application development which provides faster, efficient and good web application development environment.

➤ MVC

MVC stands for model view controller .This architecture consists of three components name model ,view and controller.

POM XML The project object model in the form of extensible markup language is used in this project to store the dependencies as well as the configuration of the project components which are used by the maven to build the project later.

➤ H2 DB(H2 Database)

The H2 database is a java based database on SQL. Its features-very fast,efficient,extremely easy to setup,in-memory database

➤ Java Spring Framework

With the help of this framework it is faster and easier to develop and test web application ,it is especially used for developing web applications, it is open source and free to use framework. Although the Spring Framework is powerful and comprehensive, configuring, setting up, and deploying Spring applications still requires considerable time and knowledge. Spring Boot alleviates this overhead with three key features.

Synchronize across different platforms It only takes a few minutes each day to keep your to-do list up to date. A to-do list helps you reach your goals without wasting time figuring out your priorities. You'll be more productive, forget nothing, improve time management, and handle tasks more effectively.

➤ Self-imposed deadline reminders

Task assignment when used for team task management. Use your team's to-do list to assign the best people for the job.

➤ STS 4

Spring tool suite version 4 is IDE specially developed for developing the standalone web application based on eclipse IDE ,it makes it faster ,efficient and more convenient.

➤ Maven plugin

It is the project management tool used to manage the files of a project efficiently it is majorly based on POM model. POM stands for project object model.

V. FUTURE SCOPE

The future of the application looks promising, with new technologies and trends emerging that are likely to shape the industry in the coming years. There are many things which can be improved in the future. New functionality for sharing some basic tasks can be shared with other people or exchanged in a certain that can be read directly by the web application from the local disk .Some of the future scopes of the web application are as follows:

- **Personalization:** Personalization is likely to be a significant trend in the future of application. Travelers are increasingly seeking personalized experiences.
- **Virtual and Augmented Reality**
- **Sustainability**
- **Voice Search**
- **Blockchain Technology**
- **Social Media Integration**
- **Sustainable Environment**

VI. CONCLUSION

The project can be used to manage the daily task needs of the user.The basic needs for the use of the software have been met by the software as it is secured,and easy to use. The main aim was to learn how to work in a team and how it feels like to work in a project with professional developers who have years of experience. The second aim for this project was to apply what I've learned about various web development technologies. To learn the best practices used in web development. Learned a lot about dynamic websites, server side rendering and how to create a good web design

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